

THE PROBLEM OF COMORBIDITY IN THE TREATMENT OF DISEASES OF INTERNAL ORGANS

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Annotation. This review summarizes numerous studies of mental factors in diseases of internal organs. The role of mental state in the diagnosis, course, assessment of severity, prognosis and treatment of somatic diseases is shown.

Key words: patients, internal diseases, treatment, comorbidity.

Introduction. In recent years, more and more attention has been paid to the features of diagnosis and treatment of patients with a combination of two or more diseases. The coexistence of diseases is often described in domestic works as combined, concomitant, associated diseases and conditions. In foreign scientific literature, the terms comorbid diseases, comorbid conditions, comorbidity, multimorbidity are more often used. Many years of clinical and scientific experience, analysis of numerous studies made it possible to formulate the main positions on the problem of comorbidity in the form of abstracts with a brief rationale and comments.

Comorbid diseases are common, especially in older patients. Doctors often have to manage patients with a combination of several diseases. An analysis of a 10-year study of patients with six common chronic diseases found that half of older patients with arthritis had hypertension, 20% had cardiovascular disease, 14% had diabetes, and 12% had a mental disorder [1]. More than 60% of patients with asthma reported coexisting arthritis, 20% had cardiovascular disease, and 16% had diabetes, and among patients with cardiovascular disease, 60% had arthritis, 20% had diabetes, and 10% had asthma or mental problems.

In elderly patients with chronic kidney disease, the incidence of coronary heart disease (CHD) is 22% higher, and new coronary events are 3.4 times higher compared to patients without impaired renal function [2].

With the development of end-stage renal failure requiring replacement therapy, the incidence of chronic ischemic heart disease is 24.8%, and myocardial infarction is 8.7% (United States Renal Data System, 2002). In addition, chronic kidney disease is a high risk factor for complications of coronary artery disease [3]. The number of comorbid diseases increases significantly with age. Multimorbidity increases from 10% in patients under 19 years of age to 80% in people 80 years of age and older [4, 5].

The increased incidence of comorbidity cannot be explained solely by the high prevalence of diseases. Research shows that the high prevalence of disease combinations cannot be fully explained by mathematical multiplication of frequencies alone. The following typology of disease comorbidity can be proposed:

- random - random combination;
- causal - a common cause causes both diseases;
- complicated - the main disease causes another;
- unspecified - the conditions are related, but the causal relationships are not precisely defined.

The non-random nature of the association of diseases may be due to common causes, risk factors and nonspecific pathophysiological mechanisms. In particular, the hepatitis C virus can cause glomerulonephritis, peripheral neuropathy, myocarditis, thyroiditis and other diseases [6].

Known risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, diabetes and smoking are common risk factors for coronary artery disease, ischemic stroke, intermittent claudication, heart failure, chronic kidney disease, and erectile dysfunction.

Universal nonspecific pathophysiological mechanisms play an important role in the development of multimorbidity. The increased risk of cardiovascular diseases

in patients with chronic inflammatory diseases cannot be explained solely by the influence of traditional risk factors. It has been found that inflammation plays an important role not only in the development of arthritis and systemic connective tissue diseases, but also in vascular atherosclerosis.

In patients with comorbid diseases, the severity of the condition increases and the prognosis worsens. Practicing physicians are well aware that the presence of concomitant diseases negatively affects the course and outcome of diseases. Research confirms these observations. In particular, comorbid diseases, especially cardiovascular diseases, significantly (+78%) increase mortality in patients with type II diabetes on peritoneal dialysis [8].

Among patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease receiving long-term oxygen therapy, in the case of a Charlson comorbidity index equal to 0; 1 or 2 or more mortality after 3 years was 55; 64.5 and 82.3%, respectively [9]. For every 10% decrease in forced expiratory volume in 1 second, cardiovascular mortality in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease increases by 28%.

Comorbidity must be taken into account when diagnosing diseases. Many diseases have similar clinical and laboratory manifestations, making timely diagnosis difficult. In some cases of chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, serious difficulties arise in diagnosing coronary artery disease. For example, during an exacerbation of asthma, 70% of patients experience chest discomfort. On the other hand, in patients with chest discomfort and a negative stress test, bronchial hyperresponsiveness is detected in 60%. Chest discomfort in obstructive pulmonary diseases is usually associated with tracheitis or severe cough, which can lead to periosteal ruptures and entrapment of the intercostal muscles. In these cases, discomfort and pain are musculoskeletal in nature and are aggravated by deep breathing and coughing.

Difficulties often arise when performing stress tests, since exercise tolerance is reduced due to respiratory failure, there are nonspecific repolarization disorders on the electrocardiogram, and β -agonists can cause sinus tachycardia and cardiac

arrhythmias. It is important to remember that dipyridamole is contraindicated in case of bronchial obstruction, and if a pharmacological stress test is necessary in patients with stable bronchial obstruction, 50 mg of aminophylline can be pre-administered. In some cases, diagnosing a concomitant disease may not be appropriate at all. For example, in women over 60 years of age with heart failure, screening for colorectal cancer is unlikely to be warranted because the benefits of cancer diagnosis are outweighed by short life expectancy.

Treatment of the disease requires taking into account comorbidity. Many drugs have a complex mechanism of action associated with various organs and tissues. So, if there is significant impairment of kidney and liver function, it is necessary to change the doses of drugs that are primarily excreted through the kidneys or metabolized in the liver. For example, if the glomerular filtration rate is less than 10 ml/min, the dose of lovastatin, fluvastatin, simvastatin should be reduced by 50%, but the dosage of atorvastatin and pravastatin does not change.

In recent years, an increase in mortality has been shown when β_2 -agonists are used in patients with asthma, especially when used as monotherapy in young people. It is no coincidence that the FDA has banned the use of β_2 -agonists in asthma without concomitant corticosteroid therapy. Undoubtedly, in patients with coronary artery disease, the risk of using these drugs should be higher, as well as a high risk factor for cardiovascular diseases.

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, especially selective ones, increase the risk of thrombosis and are not indicated in patients with coronary artery disease or a high risk of ischemic stroke.

In patients with community-acquired pneumonia, comorbidity with other diseases of internal organs is associated with an increased risk of complications and mortality, which requires more active antibacterial therapy.

For patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and comorbidities, including diabetes or heart failure, doctors are more likely to prescribe antibiotics.

In these cases, more active drugs with a broad spectrum are selected, for example, respiratory fluoroquinolones.

Treatment of several diseases requires taking into account the interaction of medications. Selection of medications for the treatment of several diseases can cause difficulties in taking into account the interaction of various drugs.

In 20-30% of cases, patients with arterial hypertension simultaneously take non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. The latter reduce the antihypertensive effect of beta-blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors, and, to a lesser extent, thiazides and have little effect on the antihypertensive effect of calcium antagonists. Treatment of hyperthyroidism with thyreostatic drugs requires consideration of the increased risk of neutropenia in patients using angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors. Correction of erectile dysfunction with sildenafil can lead to severe hypotension in patients taking nitrates.

Comorbid diseases require a significant increase in medical resources. Comorbidity represents a serious problem for healthcare, since the treatment of several diseases requires increased costs and is difficult in the context of the continued narrow specialization of medical institutions and departments.

In patients with diabetes, the presence of diabetes-related and non-diabetic comorbidities significantly increases health care resource utilization. For example, in the absence or presence of 1, 2, 3 or more concomitant diseases, the frequency of contacts with a general practitioner was 9, 14, 21 and 29%, the issuance of prescriptions was 18, 26, 40 and 57%, the number of hospitalizations per year was 1.7; 2.3; 2.9 and 3.2%, average length of stay in hospital - 6.7; 6.3; 8.0 and 11.2 days, total long-term hospitalization - 10.7; 14.8; 22.4 and 31.9 days, respectively.

Conclusions. It is advisable to include sections on comorbid diseases and conditions in recommendations for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases. Comorbid diseases and conditions can significantly affect the diagnosis and treatment of patients. If existing recommendations are used without taking into account comorbidity, especially in the elderly, then treatment may be unsafe.

Therefore, it is important to include appropriate sections on the management of common comorbid conditions in recommendations for practicing physicians.

In contrast to the common disease-oriented recommendations with a section on comorbid diseases, a different approach is proposed, based on an integral (holistic, holistic) approach to the patient. Such patient-centered recommendations should include a discussion of diagnosis and management of patients, taking into account vital aspects of functioning, state of mind, risk factors and existing diseases.

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